

SIMPLY ADDING these previous numbers suggests that, pre-Gaia, some 40 000 δ Sct variables were known, of which around 3000 were in the LMC.

Within the DR2 variability analysis, and given that the δ Sct and SX Phe types cannot easily be distinguished without metallicity or other population-class indicator, Holl et al. (2018) assigned 8882 variables to a combination of the two. Their comparison with the Catalina catalogue of Drake et al. (2014) suggests completeness of 99%, with a contamination of 13%. They provide figures showing their sky distribution (Fig. 4, above), magnitude distribution (Fig. 5), and example light curves (Fig. 7).

With its extended 34-month temporal coverage, Gaia DR3 tabulates more than 10 million stars as variable (Eyer et al., 2023). As a result of period search and time-series modelling, they assigned 748 058 of these to a combination of δ Sct, γ Dor, and SX Phe variables. Of these (Rimoldini et al., 2023, Table 3), at least 12 000 (and probably many more) are likely to be δ Sct. As expected from the Kepler insights into their amplitude distribution, the sample is dominated by low-amplitude candidates (< 0.01 mag for 537 769 sources), which are therefore also expected to be significantly contaminated.

ONE OBJECTIVE of the new Gaia-enabled studies is to characterise the period–luminosity relation as a function of pulsation mode and metallicity, using the Gaia parallaxes and extinction corrections to determine absolute magnitudes.

Ziaali et al. (2019) examined 1500 stars from previous compilations including Kepler, based on DR2. Many fall on a period–luminosity sequence coinciding with the fundamental radial-mode pulsation. But others fall on a second ridge that is a factor two shorter in period. Seen more clearly in the TESS–DR3 sample of Barac et al. (2022, Fig. 2), and with several of them showing amplitude modulation on timescales of years, they suggest that this may signify a transfer of energy between modes, and hence a transient nature of the secondary ridge.

In a similar approach using 8400 δ Sct from ASAS–SN, Jayasinghe et al. (2020) found that the fundamental-mode pulsators have periods dependent on metallicity. They also identified a period-dependent Galactic scale height, and a median period increasing with Galactocentric radius, indicative of a radial metallicity gradient.

From a larger sample of 15 000 TESS stars, Gootkin et al. (2024) found that the pulsator fraction within the instability strip peaks at 50–70%, of which 85% of the variables are probable δ Sct stars (the others being hybrid or γ Dor pulsators). They also identified a correlation between pulsator fraction and spectral line broadening as determined from the Gaia RVS instrument, confirming that rotation has a driving role the δ Sct pulsations.

Other details of the period–luminosity relation are revealing more complex dependencies on surface gravity and temperature, and confirming the power of combining TESS and Gaia for studies of pulsating stars (Poro et al., 2021; Read et al., 2024; Poro et al., 2024).

RELATED GOAL of the Gaia δ Sct studies has been to accurately place them in the Hertzsprung–Russell diagram, and to characterise their complex variability as a function of location. A specific objective is to clarify the long-standing question of whether all stars in the instability strip pulsate or, alternatively, why many of the stars in the δ Sct instability strip do not.

The background to this interesting problem (Murphy et al., 2019) is that the δ Sct variables, of mass 1.5 – $2.3M_{\odot}$, occupy a region of the main sequence where the depth of the surface convection zone is a steep function of effective temperature, and consequently where time-dependent convection models are needed to accurately model the pulsations and compute instability strips (Dupret et al., 2004; Grigahcène et al., 2005).

From an original sample of 15 000 Kepler A and F stars, interpreted with the aid of Gaia DR2, Murphy et al. (2019) identified 1988 as genuine δ Sct variables (the others being mainly eclipsing binaries and γ Dor stars with harmonics or high-frequency modes). From this sample, they also found a peak pulsator fraction of 70% in the middle of the canonical instability strip, which they found to be underpopulated with pulsators at the red edge, and overpopulated beyond the blue edge.

This led them to define a new empirical luminosity-dependent instability strip, one that is systematically hotter than the theoretical boundaries currently in use. But inside even this revised instability strip, the pulsator fraction remains well below 100%, such that the ‘problem’, although alleviated, nonetheless persists.

SOME FURTHER PROGRESS was made with Gaia DR3. Murphy et al. (2024) isolated δ Sct pulsators within the Cep–Her complex, using light curves from TESS, and the colour–magnitude diagram from Gaia, to identify objects compatible with the zero-age main sequence. Here, their δ Sct pulsator fraction reached 100%, with a trend of higher pulsator fractions for younger stellar associations. They also found that rapid rotators are more likely to pulsate, specifically in low-order modes, but that they do so with less regular pulsation patterns.